

Studies on Some N-Acyl N-Phenylhydroxylamines as Metal-Complexing Ligands. Part IX. Formation Constants of UO_2^{2+} -Complexes of Some N-Hydroxysuccinamic Acids

NRIPENDRA NATH GHOSH and SUSANTA KUMAR MUKHOPADHYAY

Inorganic Chemistry Laboratory, University College of Science, Calcutta-700009.

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The first-step formation constants of UO_2^{2+} -complexes of some N-hydroxysuccinamic acids viz. N-phenyl N-hydroxysuccinamic acid (R_pH_2), N-o-tolyl N-hydroxysuccinamic acid (R_oH_2) and N-m-tolyl N-hydroxysuccinamic acid (R_mH_2) have been determined spectrophotometrically. Stabilities are in the ligand order $R_i^mH_2 > R_i^oH_2 > R_pH_2$. The first-step hydrolysis constant k' of UO_2^{2+} ion has been determined spectrophotometrically and found to be $pK' = 4.00$ at a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5$) at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ and the molar extinction coefficients of the species UO_2^{2+} and $UO_2(OH)^+$ at $\lambda = 385$ nm are found to be 2.0 and 13.0 respectively.

SOME N-acyl N-aryl hydroxylamines viz. N-phenyl N-hydroxysuccinamic acid¹ (R_pH_2), N-o-tolyl N-hydroxysuccinamic acid² (R_oH_2) and N-m-tolyl N-hydroxysuccinamic acid³ (R_mH_2) have been found to give orange colouration with UO_2^{2+} ion in aqueous solution. The existence of (1:1) orange complexes at pH values 3 to 4, have been found at $\lambda = 385$ and 490 nm by Job's method of continuous variation⁴. The formation constants of (1:1) chelates of UO_2^{2+} with the ligands R_pH_2 , R_oH_2 or R_mH_2 have been determined following Budesinsky's method of proportional absorbance⁵.

Although the hydrolysis of uranyl ion in water medium has been studied and the first-step hydrolysis constant has been determined to be 8.1×10^{-5} in 0.1M KCl by Harris and Kolthoff⁶, and 6.3×10^{-5} in 0.1M NaClO₄ medium by Rydberg⁷ respectively, this hydrolysis constant of uranyl ion in aqueous solution has been determined in 0.5M NaClO₄ medium following the spectrophotometric method of Irving, Rossotti and Harris⁸.

Let us consider a number of equimolecular solutions of $UO_2(ClO_4)_2$ and RH_2 (ligand) at a constant ionic strength having different pH values. The reaction between the ligand (RH_2) and the uranyl ion may be assumed to take place as

The equilibrium constant

$$K = \frac{M_1[H^+]^n}{M_0R_2} \quad \dots (2)$$

and the conditional stability constant K' for (1:1) complex is given by

$$K' = \frac{M_1}{(M - M_1)(R - M_1)} \quad \dots (3)$$

Again, the first-step hydrolysis of uranyl ion may be considered as

and hydrolysis constant

$$k' = \frac{M'}{M_0} [H^+] \quad \dots (4)$$

For the dissociation of RH_2 ,

dissociation constants,

$$k_1^* = \frac{R_1}{R_2} [H^+] \quad \dots (5)$$

and

$$k_1^*k_2^* = \frac{R_0}{R_2} [H^+]^2 \quad \dots (6)$$

After attainment of equilibrium at any stage,

$$M = M_0 + M_1 + M' \quad \dots (7)$$

$$R = R_0 + R_1 + R_2 + M_1 \quad \dots (8)$$

where M and R are initial concentrations of uranyl ion and ligand; M_0 , M_1 , M' , R_0 , R_1 , R_2 are equilibrium concentrations of UO_2^{2+} , $[UO_2(RH_{2-n})]^{(2-n)+}$, $[UO_2(OH)]^+$, R^{2-} , RH^- , RH_2 , respectively.

From (4), (5), (6), (7) and (8)

$$M_0 = \frac{M - M_1}{1 + \frac{k'}{[H^+]}} \quad \dots (9)$$

and

$$R_2 = \frac{R - M_1}{1 + \frac{k_1^*}{[H^+]} + \frac{k_1^* k_2^*}{[H^+]^2}} \quad \dots (10)$$

And from (2), (9) and (10),

$$K = \frac{M_1 \left(1 + \frac{k'}{[H^+]}\right) \left(1 + \frac{k_1^*}{[H^+]} + \frac{k_1^* k_2^*}{[H^+]^2}\right) [H^+]^n}{(M - M_1)(R - M_1)} \quad \dots (11)$$

Thus,

$$\log K' + \log \left(1 + \frac{k'}{[H^+]}\right) + \log \left(1 + \frac{k_1^*}{[H^+]} + \frac{k_1^* k_2^*}{[H^+]^2}\right) = n pH + \log K \quad \dots (12)$$

Plot of

$$\left[\log K' + \log \left(1 + \frac{k'}{[H^+]}\right) + \log \left(1 + \frac{k_1^*}{[H^+]} + \frac{k_1^* k_2^*}{[H^+]^2}\right) \right]$$

against pH would be linear. From the intercept log K and from the slope the value of 'n' may be found out⁸. Thus the evaluation of equilibrium constant K demands—

- (i) determination of conditional stability constant (K'),
- (ii) determination of hydrolysis constant of uranyl ion,
- (iii) concept of acid dissociation constants of the ligands.

Conditional Stability Constant (K')

Let us consider three equimolecular solutions of uranyl perchlorate and the ligand (RH₂) at different dilutions having a constant ionic strength and the same pH value. Let C_M = C_R, C'_M = C'_R and C''_M = C''_R are the concentrations of the uranyl ion and the ligand in the three solutions whose concentrations are related with each other by the relation C''_M = 0.8, C'_M = 0.64 C_M. Let C₁, C₂, C₃ are the concentrations of the complex at the three different dilutions whose optical densities are A₁, A₂, A₃ respectively.

Now for the particular pH, the conditional stability constant may be represented as

$$K' = \frac{C_1}{(C_M - C_1)^2} = \frac{C_2}{(C'_M - C_2)^2} = \frac{C_3}{(C''_M - C_3)^2} \quad \dots (13)$$

Again,

$$\frac{C_1}{C_2} = \frac{A_1}{A_2}, \quad \frac{C_1}{C_3} = \frac{A_1}{A_3} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{C_2}{C_3} = \frac{A_2}{A_3}$$

then,

$$C_2 = \frac{A_2}{A_3} C_3 \quad \text{and} \quad C_1 = \frac{A_1}{A_2} C_2 \quad \dots (14)$$

Substituting C₁ and C₂ in equation (13)

$$\frac{C_3}{\frac{A_3}{A_1} (C_M - \frac{A_1}{A_3} C_3)^2} = \frac{C_3}{\frac{A_3}{A_2} (C'_M - \frac{A_2}{A_3} C_3)^2} = \frac{C_3}{(C''_M - C_3)^2} \quad \dots (15)$$

On solving (15) three values of C₃ may be obtained. The average of the three values may be used to calculate K' from (13). In the same way, determining C₁ and C₂ from (14), K' may be calculated.

Hydrolysis of UO₂²⁺ ion (only first step)

Following the spectrophotometric technique⁸, the hydrolysis constant of uranyl ion may be determined as follows.

The observed absorbance (in 1 cm cell)

$$A = \frac{M(\epsilon_0 M_0 + \epsilon' M')}{M_0 + M'} \quad \dots (16)$$

where ε₀, ε' are molar absorptivities of UO₂²⁺ and UO₂(OH)⁺ ions respectively.

From (4) and (16)

$$\frac{A}{M} = \frac{\epsilon_0 + \frac{\epsilon' k'}{[H^+]}}{1 + \frac{k'}{[H^+]}}$$

This may be represented as—

$$pH = \log(A - M\epsilon_0) - \log(M\epsilon' - A) + pk' \quad \dots (17)$$

Differentiating (17) with respect to pH

$$\frac{dA}{d(pH)} = \frac{2.303(A - M\epsilon_0)(M\epsilon' - A)}{(M\epsilon' - M\epsilon_0)}$$

and

$$\frac{d^2 A}{d(pH)^2} = \frac{(2.303)^2 (A - M\epsilon_0)(M\epsilon' - A)(M\epsilon' + M\epsilon_0 - 2A)}{(M\epsilon' - M\epsilon_0)^2}$$

At the stationary point of $\frac{dA}{d(pH)}$,

$$\frac{d^2 A}{d(pH)^2} = 0$$

then A = either $\frac{M\epsilon' + M\epsilon_0}{2}$ or Mε' or Mε₀.

Again,

$$\frac{d^2A}{d(pH)^2} = \frac{(2.303)^2}{(Me' - Me_0)^2} [(A - Me_0)(Me' - A)^2 \\ \times (Me' + Me_0 - 2A) \\ - (A - Me_0)^2(Me' - A) \\ \times (Me' + Me_0 - 2A) \\ - 2(A - Me_0)^2(Me' - A)^2]$$

when

$$A = \frac{Me' + Me_0}{2}, \quad \frac{d^2A}{d(pH)^2} = -ve,$$

a maximum on the plot of $\frac{dA}{d(pH)}$ against pH is indicated.

Substitution of $A = \frac{Me' + Me_0}{2}$ in equation (17) —

$$pH = pk'.$$

Therefore the pH value corresponding to the maximum (where $A = \frac{Me' + Me_0}{2}$) of the curve $\frac{dA}{d(pH)}$ vs pH , gives pk' .

The value of hydrolysis constant thus obtained can be refined as follows

From equations (4) and (16) —

$$A \left(1 + \frac{k'}{[H^+]}\right) = Me' \frac{k'}{[H^+]} + Me_0. \quad \dots (18)$$

A plot of $A \left(1 + \frac{k'}{[H^+]}\right)$ against $\frac{k'}{[H^+]}$ gives a straight line from the intercept the value of Me_0 and the slope Me' may be obtained. Again the equation (18) may be arranged as —

$$\log(A - Me_0) - \log(Me' - A) = pH - pk'. \quad \dots (19)$$

Using the calculated values of Me_0 and Me' , the plot of $\log(A - Me_0) - \log(Me' - A)$ against pH should be linear, from the intercept pk' may be found out. Thus by the method of successive approximation the refined value of the hydrolysis constant may be found out.

Dissociation constants of the ligands

The acid dissociation constants of the ligands have been determined¹⁰ by applying Bjerrum's method¹¹ with appropriate modifications^{12,13}. The formation curves are obtained by plotting $\bar{n}_H$ vs pH and the acid dissociation constants are evaluated by Bjerrum's half- $\bar{n}$ method.

Formation constants of UO_2^{2+} -complexes

The formation constant β of the complex $[UO_2R_nH_{2-n}]^{(2-n)+}$ may be evaluated as

$$\beta = \frac{M_1}{[UO_2^{2+}][R^{2-}][H^+]^{(2-n)}} \\ = \frac{M_1}{M_0 R_0 [H^+]^{(2-n)}} \\ = \frac{M_1 [H^+]^2}{M_0 R_2 (k_1^*) (k_2^*) [H^+]^{(2-n)}} \quad [\text{From (6)}] \\ = \frac{M_1 [H^+]^n}{M_0 R_2} \cdot \frac{1}{k_1^* k_2^*} \\ = \frac{K}{k_1^* k_2^*}$$

Hence

$$\log \beta = \log K + pk_1^* + pk_2^*. \quad \dots (20)$$

Experimental

All chemicals used were either A.R. quality or properly purified. Solutions were made with doubly distilled water. Freshly prepared recrystallised R_pH_2 , $R_t^oH_2$ and $R_t^mH_2$ were used. Uranyl perchlorate solution was standardised by estimating uranium as oxinate and also by precipitating it with ammonium hydroxide followed by igniting the precipitate to U_3O_8 . Free acid in this solution was determined by passing the uranyl perchlorate solution through cation exchanger (H-form). Optical densities were measured with a spectrophotometer (UVISPEK) using 1 cm quartz cell against water as blank. pH values were adjusted with a Cambridge pH -meter (Portable type).

(a) Conditional stability constants

A number of equimolecular solutions of uranyl perchlorate and the ligand R_pH_2 , $R_t^oH_2$ or $R_t^mH_2$ at a constant ionic strength $\mu = 0.5$, having different pH values were made upto 25 ml ($2.52 \times 10^{-3} M$). Optical densities of these solutions were measured against water at 385 and 490 nm. 20 ml of each of the solutions was diluted with 0.5M $NaClO_4$ solution to 25 ml ($2.016 \times 10^{-3} M$) and optical densities of these solutions were measured at 385 and 490 nm after recording pH values. 20 ml of the diluted solutions were further diluted with 0.5M $NaClO_4$ solution to 25 ml ($1.613 \times 10^{-3} M$), pH values and optical densities against water at 385 and 490 nm were measured. Optical densities of the solutions at the three different dilutions containing the ligand R_pH_2 , were plotted against corresponding pH values (Fig. 1). Similar curves were also plotted regarding other two ligands $R_t^oH_2$ and $R_t^mH_2$. Absorbances at the different dilutions at a particular pH were obtained from the curves. Concentrations of the complexes at different dilutions were then calculated using relations (14) and (15). Conditional stability constants were obtained from the relations given in

TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS AND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF (1 : 1) UO_2^{2+} -COMPLEXES

$\lambda = 385 \text{ nm and } 490 \text{ nm, temp.} = 30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ, pk' = 4.00, \mu = 0.5$

Ligand	pH	log K'		$\log \frac{(1+k'/[H^+]) + k_1*k_2*/[H^+]^2}{(1+k_1*[H^+]) + k_1*k_2*/[H^+]^2}$	No. of protons liberated	Equilibrium constants—log K		Formation constants log $\beta = \log K + pk_1^* + pk_2^*$	Formation Constants—(1 : 1) Fe^{3+} -complexes log β
		385 nm	490 nm			385 nm	490 nm		
$R_4^0H_2$	3.20	2.72	2.71	0.10	2	-3.58	-3.60	(-3.59+4.32+8.56) = 9.29	14.10
	3.40	3.07	3.03	0.15					
	3.60	3.37	3.37	0.24					
	3.80	3.61	3.57	0.36					
R_pH_2	3.20	2.64	2.61	0.10	2	-3.69	-3.72	(-3.70+4.32+8.64) = 9.26	13.58
	3.40	2.94	2.92	0.15					
	3.60	3.31	3.28	0.24					
	3.80	3.53	3.53	0.36					
$R_t^mH_2$	3.20	2.62	2.62	0.10	2	-3.68	-3.69	(-3.68+4.32+8.80) = 9.44	13.67
	3.40	2.98	2.95	0.15					
	3.60	3.28	3.28	0.24					
	3.80	3.50	3.54	0.36					

equation (13). The average of three values were taken. Results are stated in Table 1.

Fig. 1.

Plots of optical density versus pH for UO_2^{2+} - R_pH_2 system.

- ■ Conc. of UO_2^{2+} and $R_pH_2 = 2.52 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$
- ▲ ▲ " " " = $2.015 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$
- ◻ ● " " " = $1.613 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$

(b) Hydrolysis constant of UO_2^{2+} ion (only first-step)

To determine the hydrolysis constant by spectrophotometric method⁸, wavelength 385 nm was chosen. A number of 0.012M uranyl perchlorate solutions having ionic strength $\mu = 0.5$ and at different pH values, were taken for studies. Optical densities of the solutions were measured at 385 nm.

From the absorbancy data, $\frac{\Delta A}{\Delta(pH)}$ values were calculated and plotted against the mean of two respective pH values i.e., $\frac{1}{2}(pH' + pH'')$ (Fig. 2). The

maximum of the curve at the pH value 4.01 corresponds to pk' . By method of successive approximation using equations (18) and (19) the refined values of ϵ_0 , ϵ' and pk' were found to be 2.0, 13.0 and 4.00 respectively.

Fig. 2.

Plots of $\frac{\Delta A}{\Delta(pH)}$ versus $\frac{1}{2}(pH' + pH'')$.

Hydrolysis const. of UO_2^{2+} in aqueous soln. (only first step)
conc. of $UO_2^{2+} = 0.01196 \text{ M}$

Discussion

The formation constants of UO_2^{2+} -complexes have been determined following spectrophotometric technique of Budessinky's proportional absorbance. Results are stated in Table 1. Employing the equation (12), equilibrium constants of the complex formation reactions of the metal ions and the ligand molecules

at $\lambda = 385$ nm, have been determined by the linear plot method (Fig. 3). Almost identical straight lines have also been obtained on plotting data found at $\lambda = 490$ nm. From the slope of the straight lines the number of protons liberated in the complex formation has been found to be 2. Hence it may be predicted that the first-step complex formation reactions proceeds as

Plots of $\left[\log K' + \log \left(1 + \frac{k'}{[\text{H}^+]} \right) + \log \left(1 + \frac{k_1^*}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{k_2^* k_3^*}{[\text{H}^+]^2} \right) \right]$ versus pH at $\lambda = 385$ nm.

- R_t^oH_2 , $\log K = -3.58$
 ● R_pH_2 , $\log K = -3.69$
 ▲ R_t^mH_2 , $\log K = -3.68$

Thus the ligands RH_2 act as biprotic tridentate ones and evidently the (1:1) complexes (UO_2R) would be nonelectrolyte chelates. As $[\text{UO}_2\text{R}]$ are soluble in water, they appear to be highly aquated species.

The stabilities of UO_2^{2+} -chelates are in the ligand order $\text{R}_t^m\text{H}_2 > \text{R}_t^o\text{H}_2 > \text{R}_p\text{H}_2$. The trends, the more basic are the ligands the more stable are their chelates, have been observed in many cases^{14,15}. The ligands R_t^mH_2 and R_pH_2 follow the trends but regarding R_t^oH_2 it is anomalous. The first-step stability constants of Fe^{3+} -chelates of the ligands R_pH_2 , R_t^oH_2 and R_t^mH_2 have been determined following the same procedure¹⁶. The values of the Fe^{3+} -chelates (shown in Table 1) are much greater than those of the corresponding UO_2^{2+} -chelates.

Differences in stabilities of the metal chelates have often been attributed to variation in the (charge)²/radius ratios and electronegativities of the central metal ion^{14,17}. In general, the stabilities of the metal chelates increases with increase of charge and electronegativity and decrease of radius. The decreased stabilities of UO_2^{2+} -chelates are therefore in agreement with general behaviour.

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